

Is there a flaw in the application of the no-communication theorem ?

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An experiment is proposed which seems to contradict the no-communication theorem. The experimental set up is based on entangled counter propagating photons and linear optical elements as beam splitters , polarizers and polarization rotators.

By rotating or not the polarization of one photon the appearance of fringes can be controlled on the detection of the other entangled photon without the need of coincidence counts.

The reasons why this experiment contradicts the no-communication theorem are analyzed and discussed.

First a simple one photon thought experiment is studied which demonstrates what could be wrong with the no-communication theorem.

Overlapping two beams density matrix.

When two coherent almost parallel beams are overlap at small angle a series of interference fringes are produced.

In figure 1 two beams propagates in the z-x plane and the observation screen is in the x-y plane at $z=0$.

Figure 1

If the two plane waves are of the same intensity , polarization and frequency the phase difference at the observation screen is :

$$\Delta \Phi(x) = \frac{4\pi x}{\lambda} \sin(\theta)$$

This phase difference produces fringes in the observation screen , when the phase difference is zero there is a maximum of intensity , in points where the phase difference is π the fringe is dark.

The two coherent beams can be produced in many ways.

One option is using a plane wave polarized at 45° and with a polarizing beam splitter separate the vertical and horizontal polarizations , rotate the horizontal one to vertical and then overlap the two vertical polarized beams as is shown in figure 2.

Figure 2

The vertical and horizontal polarizations can be represented by the vector states :

$$|V\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 1 \\ 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

$$|H\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} 0 \\ 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

A general state is given by

$$|\Psi\rangle = a.|V\rangle + b.|H\rangle = \begin{pmatrix} a \\ b \end{pmatrix}$$

with the normalization as usual $a.a^* + b.b^* = 1$

After the polarizing beam splitting the polarizations are separated into two beams.

Now the polarization of one of the beams can be rotated 45 degrees , for example the beam with horizontal polarization can be converted to a vertical one.

The matrix transformation is :

$$T1 = |V\rangle\langle H| = \begin{pmatrix} 0 & 1 \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix}$$

The two vertical polarized beams can be overlapped and interfere one with the other and at least two fringes may arise, during overlapping a phase factors are introduced given by :

$$\alpha = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \sin(\theta)$$

$$\Psi_f = (|V\rangle \cdot a \cdot e^{i\alpha x} + |V\rangle \cdot b \cdot e^{-i\alpha x}) = |V\rangle (a \cdot e^{i\alpha x} + b \cdot e^{-i\alpha x})$$

The matrix that represent this evolution is

$$T = |V\rangle\langle V| \cdot e^{i\alpha x} + |V\rangle\langle H| \cdot e^{-i\alpha x} = \begin{pmatrix} e^{i\alpha x} & e^{-i\alpha x} \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} \quad (3.1)$$

This matrix transformation has zero determinant, it is not unitary.

This simple process is represented by a non unitary matrix and is a real one that can be implemented using linear optics elements.

Note that the non signal theorem and others are based on unitary transformations but here there is a simple example of a non unitary one which preserves energy and probability.

As a consequence not all the conclusions based on using unitary transformations may be valid. In particular may be possible to send signals using entanglement if this type of non unitary time evolutions are involved in the experiment.

There is another way to interpret the interference by polarization rotation.

Instead of assuming the the state changes assume that the state remains the same but what changes is the operator that represent the measurement.

The operator that transforms the state is given by 3.1 and is called T.

The probability of detecting a photon at x is then given by :

$$P_x = \langle T \Psi | T \Psi \rangle = \langle \Psi | T^\dagger T \Psi \rangle$$

The new operator which gives the probability of detecting a photon at x is then

$$O_x = T^\dagger T = \begin{pmatrix} e^{-i\alpha x} & 0 \\ e^{i\alpha x} & 0 \end{pmatrix} \begin{pmatrix} e^{i\alpha x} & e^{-i\alpha x} \\ 0 & 0 \end{pmatrix} = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & e^{-i2\alpha x} \\ e^{i2\alpha x} & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

which is an Hermitian operator and has as average value

$$P_x = \langle \Psi | O_x \Psi \rangle = a^*(a + b e^{-i2\alpha x}) + b^*(a e^{+i2\alpha x} + b) = a^* \cdot a + a^* \cdot b \cdot e^{-i2\alpha x} + b^* \cdot a \cdot e^{+i2\alpha x} + b^* \cdot b$$

$$P_x = (a e^{+i\alpha x} + b e^{-i\alpha x})^* \cdot (a e^{+i\alpha x} + b e^{-i\alpha x}) = |a e^{+i\alpha x} + b e^{-i\alpha x}|^2$$

But note that now the operator which gives the probability of founding a photon at x changes from

$$O_x = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

to

$$O_x = \begin{pmatrix} 1 & e^{-i2\alpha x} \\ e^{i2\alpha x} & 1 \end{pmatrix}$$

A new x dependency is introduced due to the setup changes.

Using this interpretation the density matrix is not changed but the operator that represents the measurement does.

That is another explanation for the contradiction with the no-communication theorem.

There is no change in the density matrix, but the changes in the measurement setup changes the corresponding operator that represents the detection of a photon on the screen and in particular introduces a dependency on a new parameter x .

If the interfering beams are not plane waves the results founded above can be easily extended by allowing the amplitudes to depend on x .

With $a(x)=b(x)$ the fringes are just modulated in intensity by $|a(x)|^2$.

Proposed experiment using Entangled Source

Base on the conclusions of the previous paragraph an experiment is proposed to test the validity of the non-communication theorem.

A source capable of generate a pair of entangled photons is required, one propagating to the left the other to the right.

The photons are entangled in polarization and momentum, if the left propagating photon is in vertical polarization the right one is in horizontal.

In the same way if the left photon is horizontal polarized the right one is found in vertical polarization.

The possible initial states can be expressed as :

$$\Psi_0 = \frac{(|V\rangle|K\rangle \pm e^{i\phi}|H\rangle|K'\rangle)}{\sqrt{2}}$$

where $|K\rangle$ denotes either the $|V\rangle$ or the $|H\rangle$ polarization states, but K and K' cannot be the same.

For example the following one will be selected, but the same conclusions apply for any of the others.

$$\Psi_0 = \frac{(|V\rangle|H\rangle - |H\rangle|V\rangle)}{\sqrt{2}}$$

This state is entangled in any polarization base, for example is a base at 45 degrees is used

$$|45\rangle = \frac{(|H\rangle + |V\rangle)}{\sqrt{2}}$$

$$|-45\rangle = \frac{(|H\rangle - |V\rangle)}{\sqrt{2}}$$

$$|H\rangle = \frac{(|45\rangle + |-45\rangle)}{\sqrt{2}}$$

$$|V\rangle = \frac{(|45\rangle - |-45\rangle)}{\sqrt{2}}$$

$$\Psi_0 = \frac{(|45\rangle|-45\rangle - |-45\rangle|45\rangle)}{\sqrt{2}}$$

The probability of finding a photon with polarization at 45 degrees or -45 degrees are equal both to $\frac{1}{2}$ and independent of the transverse position x of the beam.

The first but incorrect transformation that may be tried is to swap the polarizations of one photon. For example let's separate photon at A with a polarizing beam splitter and swap the H polarization to V.

The new state became :

$$\Psi_0 = \frac{(|V\rangle|H\rangle - |V\rangle|V\rangle)}{\sqrt{2}} = |V\rangle \frac{(|H\rangle - |V\rangle)}{\sqrt{2}}$$

Which is a product of two states , now the photons are not entangled any more.

But this transformation is not only not unitary also it cannot be realized by any combination of optical elements.

There is no way that two coherent beams can be overlapped without at least creating two interference fringes.

But the transformation proposed in the next section can be realized and gives the correct new state.

Transformation of the initial state

The transformation are the same as previously used for a single photon .

As can be seen in figure 3 , the left propagating photon is incident over a polarizing beam splitter which splits the incident state in two polarized beams

$$\Psi_1 = \frac{|V\rangle|H\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$$

$$\Psi_2 = \frac{|H\rangle|V\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$$

Using a half wave plate the polarization of the beam Ψ_1 is rotated 90 degrees from vertical to horizontal

$$\Psi_1 = \frac{|V\rangle|H\rangle}{\sqrt{2}} \rightarrow \frac{|H\rangle|H\rangle}{\sqrt{2}}$$

Now the two beams are spatially overlapped again using a couple of adjacent mirrors, but note that two coherent beams cannot be spatially overlapped without at least creating two fringes one bright and the other dark.

Figure 3

After overlapping the beams the new state is :

$$\Psi_2 = \frac{(|H\rangle|H\rangle e^{i\alpha x} + |H'\rangle|V\rangle e^{-i\alpha x})}{\sqrt{2}} = |H\rangle \frac{(|H\rangle e^{i\alpha x} + |V\rangle e^{-i\alpha x})}{\sqrt{2}} \quad (6.1)$$

with α given by

$$\alpha = \frac{2\pi}{\lambda} \sin(\theta) \quad (6.2)$$

It is assumed that an extra 180 phase change is introduced in the left photons to align the phases at the central point before merging.

Note that one of now horizontal polarized left propagating beams has been called H' , instead of H . This is because strictly speaking the two beams are almost but not exactly collinear.

Nevertheless at the left detection screen the amplitudes add like the classical electromagnetic force of two modes add up, so the transition amplitude is correctly expressed in 6.1.

It is also assumed that the left photon is absorbed earlier than the entangled one at the right.

Also ,depending on the details of the optical set up , reflection of one of the beams may be necessary in order to overlap the corrected entangled rays at the same border of the beams. For example in figure 3 the green ray must be in both beams at the bottom before the merge can be done , so one of the beams must be vertically inverted. (a pair of convergent lens of the same focal length can be used for that purpose).

Now the state can be factorized in polarization , it now behaves as two independence photons , one with horizontal polarization to the left.
But still they are entangled in momentum.

If on the right propagating beam a measurement of the polarization at 45 degrees is done the amplitude for that state is :

$$\Psi_2 = |H\rangle \frac{(|45\rangle + |-45\rangle)e^{i\alpha x} + (|45\rangle - |-45\rangle)e^{-i\alpha x}}{2\sqrt{2}}$$

$$\Psi_2 = |H\rangle \frac{(|45\rangle(e^{i\alpha x} + e^{-i\alpha x}) + |-45\rangle(e^{i\alpha x} - e^{-i\alpha x}))}{2\sqrt{2}}$$

$$\Psi_2 = |H\rangle \frac{(\cos(\alpha x)|45\rangle + i \sin(\alpha x)|-45\rangle)}{2\sqrt{2}}$$

The amplitude at 45 degrees is

$$A_{(45)} = \frac{(e^{i\alpha x} + e^{-i\alpha x})}{2} = \cos(\alpha x)$$

In the same way the amplitude of polarization at -45 degrees is :

$$A_{(45)} = \frac{(e^{i\alpha x} - e^{-i\alpha x})}{2} = i \cdot \sin(\alpha x)$$

There are fringes and anti fringes depending on x (momentum component p_x of the beams) without requiring coincidence counts.

But on the original state Ψ_0 the amplitudes were

$$\Psi_0 = \frac{(|45\rangle|-45\rangle - |-45\rangle|45\rangle)}{\sqrt{2}}$$

$$A_{(45)} = \frac{-1}{\sqrt{2}}$$

$$A_{(-45)} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{2}}$$

By rotating or not the polarization state on the left interference or lack of it results on the beam propagating to the right and that can be used to transfer information in principle instantaneously from left to right.

The fringes can be erased or not acting only in one part of the system contrary to what is stated in the non-communication theorem.

As in the case of a single no entangled photon the results of this proposed experiment can be interpreted by a change in the operator representing the measurement.

The change in the operator representing the detection of a photon at point x on the screens may explain the introduction of fringes by altering the only one of the entangled beams.

Conclusions

An experimental proposal is presented which by means of momentum entanglement transfers information (in principle instantaneously) using two opposite entangled counter propagating photons.

The key to generate a dependency on the transverse coordinate x (or what is the same the transverse component of the entangled momentum) is the merging two almost identical beams. The probability of detecting a photon in two orthogonal polarizations depends on x after some transformations on one of the opposite photons .

Nevertheless on averaging on both polarizations this dependency cancels out.

In this proposal is just the change in probability distribution of polarizations on x what is used to transfer the information.

The appearance or not of fringes can be controlled by the transformations done on only one of the subsystems.

No coincidence counts are needed to observe the fringes.

The no-communication theorem is proved for operator averages , projection measurements and other cases but not for this thought experiment.

In this proposal the operator that represents the detection of a photon at position x on the observation screen changes depending on the modifications of the experimental set up.

In particular a explicit dependency on x can be introduced by rotating or not one of the polarizations after splitting the beam on vertical and horizontal polarization and rotating the horizontal to vertical. The no-communication theorem is based on unitary transformations and then the conclusions of it may not be applicable to natural processes when the wave function collapse is mediated by interaction Hamiltonian like the one of the electric dipole approximation.

This proposed experiment can be a crucial test on the validity of the non-communication theorem as it is currently understood and applied.

May also lead to a new way of transfer information relying on entanglement.

References

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Quantum double-double-slit experiment with momentum entangled photons

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